

Efficient FIR Filter Implementation Using Approximate Multipliers for Performance Enhancement

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Approximation, Full Adder, Vedic Multiplier, FIR Filter, Image Processing	<p>Area, power, and delay form the fundamental trade-off triangle in Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) design, making simultaneous optimization of these parameters a challenging task. With the increasing demand for high-performance and low-power multimedia and signal processing applications, exact computation is often unnecessary, as minor inaccuracies do not significantly affect perceptual quality. Approximate computing exploits this error tolerance to improve hardware efficiency.</p> <p>In this work, an approximate design approach is proposed for Full Adders, Compressors, and 4x4 and 8x8 Vedic multipliers, which are employed in the implementation of an FIR low-pass filter. The proposed arithmetic units reduce logic complexity by relaxing accuracy constraints, leading to significant improvements in area utilization, power consumption, and computational delay. Vedic multiplication based on the UrdhvaTiryagbhyam sutra enables faster partial product generation and parallel computation. The performance of the proposed design is evaluated and compared with conventional exact designs using metrics such as area, power, delay, and Power Delay Product (PDP). Simulation and synthesis results obtained using ModelSim and Xilinx tools demonstrate that the proposed approximate FIR filter achieves enhanced energy efficiency while maintaining acceptable output quality for multimedia applications.</p>

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital Area, power, and delay are key parameters to be considered when designing modern digital circuits. These three parameters affect the system, and finding the optimal trade-off among them is a hard task. Balancing

these parameters is hard as improving one or two means compromising the remaining. For example, reducing power consumption may require increasing the area of the circuit which in turn may introduce significant delay in signal propagation. To address this trade-off we have

designed a filter with a compressor, a full adder and multipliers optimized for signal propagation. Optimizing speed often means increasing the transistor count, which increases the area of the circuit and hence the overall cost. Some other work on the approximate multipliers of 4x4 extended to 8x8 [1] [2]. Moreover, the authors have also proposed a new multiplier design. These designs have high accuracy values. They have done the application part employing the merging of images and JPEG (Joint Photographic Experts Group) file compression applications. In conclusion, their designs are implemented in Qflow, followed by synthesis, placement, routing, and layout visualization in Magic Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) software. HJ Kim [3], extended the approximate compressor to the Deep Learning. In this work, for Brain Floating Point 16 (bfloat16) data processing, the author designed a two-stage approximate multiplier with low cost.

Approximate computing is also applied to 6G down-link receivers [4]. This work achieved 87% savings in power consumption while simultaneously maintaining good performance metrics. Moreover, approximate multipliers are involved in wearable gadgets. In this, the successive approximation converter is involved to reduce the power consumption by 40% with good sound quality [5]. These studies concluded that approximate computing had a good balance in computational accuracy for different kinds of applications by using less power. Further, many methods are involved to achieve approximate computing, such as Cartesian genetic programming and transistor-level logic complexity reduction which give acceptable trade-offs between accuracy, area, power, and delay [6] [7] [8]. Event mathematical models are employed to verify the accuracy, propagation delay, consumption of power, area of the circuit, and output quality in various applications like adders, multipliers, and applications in digital signal processing like FIR (Finite Impulse Response) filters and DCT (Discrete Cosine Transform) [7] [8].

To practically evaluate the above designs, image processing techniques are used to showcase the real-time quality of the design. Performance metrics such as MAE (Mean Absolute Error), MSE (Mean Square Error), structural similarity index (SSIM), and peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) are commonly used for image quality evaluation. MSE, PSNR, and MAE mainly

concern themselves with error measurement without considering structural exactness. SSIM will focus on the structural and feature similarity of the image quality. These types of metrics are discussed in detail in [9]. The authors in the paper [10] present a novel approach to reducing power and circuitry area in the CMOS (Complementary Metal-Oxide Semiconductor) VLSI circuit by designing low-power FIR filters utilizing full adders and multipliers. The design of a 32-tap FIR filter by incorporating two 16-tap filters improved power and area efficiency [11]. Achieved 35% power consumption reduction and a 44% less circuit area compared to conventional radix-4 modified Booth algorithms.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In VLSI Digital Signal Processing System : Design and Implementation by K.K.Parhi. Digital audio, speech recognition, cable modems, radar, high-definition television-these are but a few of the modern computer and communications applications relying on digital signal processing (DSP) and the attendant application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs). As information-age industries constantly reinvent ASIC chips for lower power consumption and higher efficiency, there is a growing need for designers who are current and fluent in VLSI design methodologies for DSP.

Short-length FIR filters and their use in fast nonrecursive filtering by Z.-J.Mou, and P. Duhamel:

The basic tools required for an efficient use of the recently proposed fast finite impulse response (FIR) algorithms are provided. These algorithms not only reduce arithmetic complexity but also partially maintain the multiply-accumulate structure, thus resulting in efficient implementations. A set of basic algorithms is derived, together with some rules for combining them. Their efficiency is compared with that of classical schemes in the case of three different criteria, corresponding to various types of implementation. It is shown that this class of algorithms (which includes classical ones as special cases) makes it possible to find the best tradeoff corresponding to any criterion

Hardware-efficient parallel FIR filter structure based on modified Cook-Toom algorithm by Q. Tian, Y. Wang, G. Liu, X. Liu, J. Diao, and HuiXu:

The Cook-Toom algorithm is widely used in short-length linear convolution, which is the building

block of large points convolution algorithms. This paper proposes improved parallel finite impulse response (FIR) filter structures for linear-phase FIR filter, which is based on the Cook-Toom algorithm. In the proposed structures, Cook-Toom algorithm is used to reduce the number of sub-filters, and the symmetric properties of the linear-phase FIR filter's coefficients is used to further reduce the number of multipliers in sub-filters. Compared with the reported FFA and ISCA parallel FIR filter structures, the proposed method can substantially reduce the computational complexity. Specifically, for a 8-parallel 144-tap filter, the proposed design saves 18 multipliers (5%), 45 adders (7.9%) compared with the structure based on Winograd convolution algorithm [7].

Approximate 8-bit multipliers and their physical design implementation by S. Mondal, M. R, and R. S:

Approximate computing is widely used in a large number of error-tolerant applications. Multiplication is an integral arithmetic operation for many of these applications. In this paper we discuss 8 bit multiplier designs designed using approximate 4:2 compressors and encoded sum of partial products, and later introduce an approximate full adder to compute the sum of partial products in less significant bit positions. We use these techniques to systematically trade off accuracy for improvements in area, power and more significantly delay. These multipliers were designed using Verilog and synthesized using Cadence Design Suite with the help of a 45nm standard cell library. The physical designs of exact, existing and proposed multipliers were also performed using the open source RTL to GDS flow tool Q-flow. This is done to highlight the importance and reliability of open source tools in the VLSI physical design process when compared to paid software which may not be accessible to everyone.

VLSI Digital Signal Processing System : Design and Implementation by K.K.Parhi(Wiley, New York, 1999):

Digital audio, speech recognition, cable modems, radar, high-definition television-these are but a few of the modern computer and communications applications relying on digital signal processing (DSP) and the attendant application-specific integrated circuits (ASICs). As information-age industries constantly reinvent ASIC chips for lower power consumption and higher efficiency, there is a growing need for designers who are current and fluent in VLSI design methodologies for DSP.

Design and implementation of area efficient 2-parallel filters on FPGA using image system by L. K. Phimu and M. Kumar:

Parallel FIR filter is mostly used among various types of filter in Digital Signal Processing (DSP). This paper shows the design of area-efficient 2-parallel FIR filter using VHDL and its implementation on FPGA using image system. This paper gives the details basic blocks of area-efficient 2-parallel FIR digital filter. In this paper proposed 2-parallel digital FIR filter and area-efficient 2-parallel FIR filter are explained. Its simulation using Xilinx 14.2 are also discussed. It also presents the FPGA implementation of primary 2-parallel filter and area-efficient 2-parallel on Xilinx 14.2 Spartan 3E Starter Board XC3S500E chips and its results. Since adders are light weight in silicon area when compare with the multipliers, therefore multipliers are replaced by the adder to reduce area and delay of the parallel FIR filter. Xilinx ISE is used for simulating the design of the filter.

Short-length FIR filters and their use in fast nonrecursive filtering by Z.-J.Mou, and P. Duhamel:

The basic tools required for an efficient use of the recently proposed fast finite impulse response (FIR) algorithms are provided. These algorithms not only reduce arithmetic complexity but also partially maintain the multiply-accumulate structure, thus resulting in efficient implementations. A set of basic algorithms is derived, together with some rules for combining them. Their efficiency is compared with that of classical schemes in the case of three different criteria, corresponding to various types of implementation. It is shown that this class of algorithms (which includes classical ones as special cases) makes it possible to find the best tradeoff corresponding to any criterion

Hardware-efficient VLSI implementation for 3-parallel linear-phase FIR digital filter of odd length by Y.C. Tsao, and K. Choi(IEEE ISCAS, 2012):

Based on fast FIR algorithms (FFA), this paper proposes new 3-parallel finite-impulse response (FIR) filter structures, which are beneficial to symmetric convolutions of odd length in terms of the hardware cost. The proposed 3-parallel FIR structures exploit the inherent nature of the symmetric coefficients of odd length, according to the length of filter, $(N \bmod 3)$, reducing half the number of multipliers in subfilter section at the expense of additional adders in

preprocessing and postprocessing blocks. The overhead from the additional adders in preprocessing and postprocessing blocks stay fixed, not increasing along with the length of the FIR filter, whereas the number of reduced multipliers increases along with the length of the FIR filter. For example, for a 81-tap filter, the proposed A structure saves 26 multipliers at the expense of 5 adders, whereas for a 591-tap filter, the proposed structure saves 196 multipliers at the expense of 5 adders still. Overall, the proposed 3-parallel FIR structures can lead to significant hardware savings for symmetric coefficients of odd length from the existing FFA parallel FIR filter, especially when the length of the filter is large.

Hardware-efficient parallel FIR filter structure based on modified Cook-Toom algorithm by Q. Tian, Y. Wang, G. Liu, X. Liu, J. Diao, and HuiXu:

The Cook-Toom algorithm is widely used in short-length linear convolution, which is the building block of large points convolution algorithms. This paper proposes improved parallel finite impulse response (FIR) filter structures for linear-phase FIR filter, which is based on the Cook-Toom algorithm. In the proposed structures, Cook-Toom algorithm is used to reduce the number of sub-filters, and the symmetric properties of the linear-phase FIR filter's coefficients is used to further reduce the number of multipliers in sub-filters. Compared with the reported FFA and ISCA parallel FIR filter structures, the proposed method can substantially reduce the computational complexity. Specifically, for a 8-parallel 144-tap filter, the proposed design saves 18 multipliers (5%), 45 adders (7.9%) compared with the structure based on Winograd convolution algorithm [7].

Efficient implementation for 3-parallel linear-phase FIR digital odd length filters by Anjali Rao, Abhishek Kumar, Neetesh Purohit (IEEE CICT, 2020):

In this paper, we propose 3-parallel finite-impulse response (FIR) structures with the application of polyphase coefficient symmetry and fast FIR algorithms (FFAs). For symmetric convolution of odd length filter The proposed structures are beneficial in terms of the number of multipliers which can reduce the implementation complexity of the parallel FIR filters. Initially, 3-parallel traditional FIR structures are reconfigured in such a way that the polyphase coefficient symmetry of odd length FIR filters can be applied for the reduction of the half number of multipliers, thereafter, FFAs are used for lowering the parallel subfilter

branches of a polyphase filter. On comparing the performance with existing similar structures the proposed FFA based structure is found superior in terms of reduced number of required multipliers.

Exploiting coefficient symmetry in conventional polyphase FIR filters by A.Kumar, S. Yadav and N. Purohit:

The conventional polyphase architecture for linear-phase finite impulse response (FIR) filter loses its coefficient symmetry property due to the inefficient arrangement of the filter coefficients among its subfilters. Although, existing polyphase structures can avail the benefits of coefficient symmetry property, at the cost of versatility and complex subfilters arrangement of the conventional polyphase structure. To address these issues, in this paper, we first present the mathematical expressions for inherent characteristics of the conventional polyphase structure. Thereafter, we use these expressions to develop a generalized mathematical framework which exploits coefficient symmetry by retaining the direct use of conventional FIR filter coefficients. Further, the transfer function expressions for the proposed Type-1/ transposed Type-1 polyphase structures using coefficient symmetry are derived. The proposed structures can reduce the requirement of multiplier units in polyphase FIR filters by half. We also demonstrate the decimator design using the proposed Type-1 polyphase structure and the interpolator design using the proposed transposed Type-1 polyphase structure. Moreover, the phase and magnitude characteristics of the proposed Type-1/transposed Type-1 polyphase structures are presented. It is revealed via numerical examples that all subfilters of the proposed symmetric polyphase structure possess linear-phase characteristics.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

In modern Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) systems, arithmetic circuits such as adders, compressors, and multipliers form the fundamental building blocks of digital computation and signal processing applications. These circuits are essential for a wide range of digital systems, including Finite Impulse Response (FIR) filters used in multimedia, communication, and image processing. Traditionally, these arithmetic units are designed for exact computation, prioritizing accuracy above all other factors. Full adders, for instance, form the basis of addition operations by generating sum and

carry outputs for three input bits. Conventional implementations include ripple carry adders, which are simple and straightforward but suffer from linear propagation delay as the bit-width increases, and carry look-ahead adders, which improve speed by predicting carries in advance but require additional hardware, thereby increasing circuit complexity and silicon area. Complementary CMOS full adders, often employed for their noise robustness and reliability, also consume considerable area compared to alternative pass-transistor designs. While these designs ensure precise arithmetic operations, their power consumption and delay become significant concerns in high-performance systems.

Compressors are another class of arithmetic circuits widely used in multipliers to reduce the number of partial sums and accelerate addition. For example, a 4:2 compressor can take four input bits and compress them into two outputs, significantly reducing intermediate addition stages in multipliers. Conventional compressors are designed to guarantee accurate outputs, which ensures correctness in all computations but leads to higher power and area usage, particularly for larger bit-width multipliers. Carry Increment Adders (CIA) provide an alternative addition technique that improves speed over simple ripple carry adders. CIAs divide an n-bit addition into smaller blocks, calculate partial sums for each block, and use an incremental circuit to add the carry from the preceding block. While CIAs are faster than ripple carry adders for medium bit-width operations and offer moderate hardware complexity, they still require extra logic for carry increment, resulting in additional area and only partial reduction in delay. Similarly, Vedic multipliers, based on ancient Vedic mathematics, offer faster multiplication techniques using the UrdhvaTiryakbhyam sutra, which generates all partial products simultaneously.

Standard Vedic multipliers, particularly 4×4 and 8×8 implementations, are employed in digital signal processing applications such as FIR filters due to their regular structure and speed advantages over conventional shift-and-add multipliers. However, exact Vedic multipliers require multiple adders and compressors to sum the partial products, leading to higher power consumption and increased silicon area as bit-width grows.

While faster than traditional multipliers, these exact implementations still contribute to critical path delay in complex systems. FIR filters, a core component of digital signal processing, rely heavily on these arithmetic circuits for implementation. The convolution-based computation performed by FIR filters requires multiple multiplications of input signals with filter coefficients, followed by summation of the results. In conventional FIR filter designs, multipliers such as 4×4 or 8×8 Vedic multipliers are used alongside adders, including ripple carry or carry increment adders, to accumulate the results.

This exact computation guarantees output accuracy, which is crucial in applications demanding high fidelity. However, exact FIR filter implementations face several limitations. First, the repeated use of multipliers and adders results in significant power consumption, particularly when processing high-speed or high-volume data streams. Second, the critical path delay of the multipliers and adders limits the maximum operational frequency of the system, affecting real-time performance in multimedia and communication applications. Third, the area occupied by these arithmetic circuits increases with filter order and bit-width, leading to larger silicon footprint and higher fabrication costs. Conventional designs also focus primarily on accuracy and offer limited flexibility for optimization in power or area, making them less efficient for error-tolerant domains such as image and video processing where minor inaccuracies may be acceptable.

The implementation of these traditional systems typically involves hardware description languages such as VHDL or Verilog for accurate modeling of arithmetic circuits and FIR filters. Simulation tools like ModelSim are used for functional verification and timing analysis, ensuring the correctness and performance of the design before synthesis. Synthesis and implementation are commonly carried out on FPGA platforms such as Xilinx devices, which allow designers to evaluate the real hardware performance of circuits in terms of area, power, and delay. Standard metrics for performance evaluation include area measured by logic cells or lookup tables (LUTs), dynamic and static power consumption, propagation delay along the critical path, and power-delay product (PDP), which combines both energy efficiency and speed considerations. While these

exact implementations provide robust and reliable computation, they are increasingly challenged by the need for low-power, high-speed, and area-efficient designs in modern applications.

The high power consumption due to frequent switching, the large area requirement of complex multipliers and adders, and the delay imposed by critical paths limit their suitability for high-performance or portable devices. Furthermore, conventional systems do not exploit opportunities for approximation in domains where small computational errors are acceptable, such as in multimedia processing, thereby missing potential optimizations in energy efficiency and speed. Consequently, while traditional arithmetic circuits and FIR filter designs have proven effective for accurate computation, their limitations in power, area, and delay highlight the need for alternative strategies that can balance these critical design parameters more effectively.

4. IMPLEMENTATION OF PROPOSED ARCHITECTURE

The main task of an approximate full adder design is to optimize the sum and carry generation paths at the gate level. Reducing the usage of the XOR gate can address this efficiently. The gate-level designs mentioned are designed so that they have half the transistor count of the existing design or even fewer. Reducing the transistor count has significant advantages, including lower power consumption, reduced circuit area, better speed, reduced heat generation, and improved reliability. In this study, two different types of approximate designs for the full adder are suggested. These are Approximate Full Adder Design Type- 1 (AFA) [12], and the proposed full adder (Proposed AFA), i.e., the proposed design.

Figure 1: Gate-level circuit of AFA
A. Approximate Full Adder Design Type- 1 (AFA)

In this methodology [12], the AFA design consists of two OR gates and an AND gate, as depicted in Fig.1. The sum is generated by logical OR for inputs A and B, which produces a sum with four error bits, and carry is produced with an OR and an AND gate with 1 error bit.

$$\text{Sum} = A + B \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Carry} = AB + C \quad (2)$$

B. Proposed Approximate Full Adder (Proposed-AFA)

In the novel design methodology, the 010 combination's carry bit is changed from the AFA to simplify the carry expression furthermore, which is illustrated in Fig.3. Instead of an OR and an AND gate, this design simply uses a logical OR as a carry. However, the simplicity of the equation significantly reduces the circuit size and energy consumption. Moreover, the output generation has two bits of error in the carry and four bits of error in the sum. Although the accuracy is reduced, the real time performance is good enough. The following (equations (3) and (4)) exhibit the sum and carry the expression of the proposed design of the approximate computing full adder.

$$\text{Sum} = \text{Sum} = B + A \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Carry} = C + B \quad (4)$$

C. Compressor

A compressor takes several binary inputs and reduces them into fewer outputs with maximum efficiency. These circuits are of utmost significance in higher-speed arithmetic operations. A 4 : 2 compressor design is depicted in Fig.4, which takes four inputs in binary form and produces a pair of outputs, i.e., sum and carry in the form of binary. Three different types of approximate full adder circuits were elaborated, and approximate compressors were built using these full adders. For the compressor, the carry (Cout) produced in stage one is often neglected because it is considered insignificant enough to be ignored. Thus, it results in simpler circuits, reducing complexity, area, and delay propagation. Also, it leads to a simple design that speeds up the whole system with no significant sacrifice in accuracy. Fig. 5 demonstrates the comparison of area (μm^2), power (nW), propagation (ps), and Power Delay Product (PDP - fJ) of three different compression designs by proving the proposed approximate compressor (PAC) between exact compressor (EC) and Approximate Compressor (AC). In

contrast, PAC achieves acceptable efficient performance values than any other design.

4.1. DESIGN OF VEDIC MULTIPLIERS

UrdhavaTiryakbhyam is a Sanskrit word which means vertically and crosswire in English. The method is a general multiplication formula applicable to all cases of multiplication. It is based on a novel concept through which all partial products are generated concurrently. Fig. 2 demonstrates a 4 x 4 binary multiplication using this method. The method can be generalized for any N x N bit multiplication. This type of multiplier is independent of the clock frequency of the processor because the partial products and their sums are calculated in parallel. The net advantage is that it reduces the need of microprocessors to operate at increasingly higher clock frequencies. As the operating frequency of a processor increases the number of switching instances also increases. This results in more power consumption and also dissipation in the form of heat which results in higher device operating temperatures. Another advantage of UrdhvaTiryakbhyam multiplier is its scalability.

The processing power can easily be increased by increasing the input and output data bus widths since it has a regular structure. Due to its regular structure, it can be easily layout in a silicon chip and also consumes optimum area. As the number of input bits increase, gate delay and area increase very slowly as compared to other multipliers. Therefore UrdhavaTiryakbhyam multiplier is time, space and power efficient. The line diagram in fig. 2 illustrates the algorithm for multiplying two 4-bit binary numbers and . The procedure is divided into 7 steps and each step generates partial products. Initially as shown in step 1 of fig. 2, the least significant bit (LSB) of the multiplier is multiplied with least significant bit of the multiplicand (vertical multiplication). This result forms the LSB of the product. In step 2 next higher bit of the multiplier is multiplied with the LSB of the multiplicand and the LSB of the multiplier is multiplied with the next higher bit of the multiplicand (crosswire multiplication).

In order to multiply two 8-bit numbers using 4-bit multiplier we proceed as follows. Consider two 8 bit numbers denoted as AHAL and BHBL where AH and BH corresponds to the most significant 4 bits, AL and BL are the least significant 4 bits of an 8-bit number. When

the numbers are multiplied according to UrdhavaTiryakbhyam (vertically and crosswire) method, we get,

AH AL

BH BL

$$(AH \times BH) + (AH \times BL + BH \times AL) + (AL \times BL)$$

Thus we need four 4-bit multipliers and two adders to add the partial products and 4-bit intermediate carry generated. Since product of a 4 x 4 multiplier is 8 bits long, in every step the least significant 4 bits correspond to the product and the remaining 4 bits are carried to the next step. This process continues for 3 steps in this case. Similarly, 16-bit multiplier has four 8 x 8 multiplier and two 16 bit adders with 8 bit carry. Therefore, we see that the multiplier is highly modular in nature. Hence it leads to regularity and scalability of the multiplier layout.

Each block as shown above is 2x2 bit Vedic multiplier. First 2x2 bit multiplier inputs are A1A0 and B1B0. The last block is 2x2 bit multiplier with inputs A3 A2 and B3 B2. The middle one shows two 2x2 bit multiplier with inputs A3 A2 & B1B0 and A1A0 & B3 B2. So the final result of multiplication, which is of 8 bit, S7 S6 S5 S4 S3 S2 S1 S0. To understand the concept, the Block diagram of 4x4 bit Vedic multiplier is shown in Fig. 5. To get final product (S7 S6 S5 S4 S3 S2 S1 S0), four 2x2 bit Vedic multiplier (Fig. 3) and three 4-bit Ripple-Carry (RC) Adders are required. The proposed Vedic multiplier can be used to reduce delay. Early literature speaks about Vedic multipliers based on array multiplier structures. On the other hand, we proposed a new architecture, which is efficient in terms of speed. The arrangements of RC Adders shown in Fig. 5, helps us to reduce delay. Interestingly, 8x8 Vedic multiplier modules are implemented easily by using four 4x4 multiplier modules.

Figure 2: Block Diagram of 4x4 bit Vedic Multiplier

Vedic Multiplier for 8x8 bit Module:

The 8x8 bit Vedic multiplier module as shown in the block diagram in Fig. 6 can be easily implemented by using four 4x4 bit Vedic multiplier modules as discussed in the previous section. Let’s analyze 8x8 multiplications, say A= A7 A6 A5 A4 A3 A2 A1 A0 and B= B7 B6 B5B4 B3 B2 B1B0. The output line for the multiplication result will be of 16 bits as – S15 S14 S13 S12 S11 S10 S9 S8 S7 S6S5S4 S3 S2 S1 S0. Let’s divide A and B into two parts, say the 8 bit multiplicand A can be decomposed into pair of 4 bits AH-AL. Similarly, multiplicand B can be decomposed into BH-BL. The 16-bit product can be written as:

Using the fundamental of Vedic multiplication, taking four bits at a time and using 4 bit multiplier block as discussed we can perform the multiplication. The outputs of 4x4 bit multipliers are added accordingly to obtain the final product. Here total three 8 bit Ripple-Carry Adders are required as shown in Fig. 6.1

Figure 3: Block Diagram of 8x8 bit Vedic Multiplier

4.2. PROPOSED SYSTEM

FIR filter is the most widely used DSP technique. The N-tap FIR filter is normally described by the following equation.

$$y(n) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} h(i)x(n - i),$$

(1)

Where N is the number of coefficients (or taps) of the filter, h[n] represents filter coefficients, x[n], y[n] are the input and output sequences respectively. The N-tap FIR filter is characterized by N coefficients and in general, requires N multipliers and (N-1) two-input adders for implementation. Structures in which the multiplier coefficients are the same as the coefficients of the transfer function are called direct-form structures. A direct-form realization of an FIR filter can be readily developed from Eq.(1) as indicated in Figure 1 for N=4.

Figure 4: Direct form of FIR structure for N = 4

With the help of 45 nm technology, the proposed approximate compressor, adder, and Vedic Multipliers, an FIR low pass filter is designed. Comparative performance analysis of 8x8 Vedic Multiplier Fig. 3. Proposed FIR Filter block diagram of 1 megahertz is applied to the FIR filter as input, and the frequency responses of conventional and approximate FIR filters result.

The proposed system introduces a set of optimized approximate arithmetic building blocks designed to improve computational efficiency in digital signal processing applications. The architecture begins with the development of novel approximate Full Adders and 4:2 Compressors, which form the foundation for higher-level arithmetic units. By carefully relaxing certain logic conditions that have minimal impact on functional accuracy, these circuits significantly reduce transistor count, switching activity, and critical path delay. The design emphasizes achieving a favorable balance between approximation error and hardware

efficiency, ensuring suitability for error-resilient domains.

Building upon these simplified primitives, approximate Carry Increment Adders (CIAs) and 4x4 and 8x8 Vedic multipliers are constructed. The integration of approximate adders and compressors within the Vedic multiplication structure further enhances speed and reduces area and power consumption. These optimized multipliers are designed to maintain high throughput while minimizing hardware overhead, making them well-suited for real-time computation. Each module is synthesized and evaluated to quantify the improvements in area, power, delay, and Power-Delay Product (PDP) compared to conventional precise architectures.

To demonstrate the practical effectiveness of the proposed approximate modules, they are incorporated into the design of a low-pass FIR filter. Since FIR filters in multimedia and communication systems are tolerant to minor computational inconsistencies, replacing exact arithmetic units with approximate ones enables substantial improvements in hardware efficiency without degrading signal quality beyond acceptable limits. The complete system is implemented using Cadence digital design tools, while functional verification is carried out through ModelSim simulations. Further validation through Xilinx FPGA implementation confirms the real-world applicability and performance advantages of the proposed approximate architecture.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Simulation Results

Figure 4: Simulation Result

From the waveform, all input samples and coefficients are equal to 12 ($a_1 = a_2 = a_3 = a_4 = 12$ and $h_1 = h_2 = h_3 = h_4 = 12$). For a 4-tap FIR filter, the output is computed as $y = a_1 \cdot h_1 + a_2 \cdot h_2 + a_3 \cdot h_3 + a_4 \cdot h_4$. Substituting the given values, $y = (12 \times 12) + (12 \times 12) + (12 \times 12) + (12 \times 12)$. Each multiplication equals 144, and since there are four identical terms, the total becomes $4 \times 144 = 576$. Therefore, the output value $y = 576$ shown in the waveform is mathematically correct and verifies the proper operation of the FIR filter.

4.2 RTL Schematic

Figure 5: RTL Schematic of FIR Filter using Multiplier and Adders

4.3 Power Report

Figure 6: Power Report

In this simulation, we get power consumed in the design is 10.615mw.

4.4 Device utilization summary

Figure 7: Area Report

According to Area report of FIR filter, we required 879 lookup tables to perform this operation.

4.5. Timing Summary

Figure 8: Delay Report

Delay Report shows the FIR filter has a delay value of 11.463ns.

Table 1: Compression table

	EXISTING SYSTEM	PROPOSED SYSTEM
DELAY	42.643ns	11.463ns
POWER	99.343mw	10.615mw
AREA	1950	879
SPEED	23.45mz	87.12mz
PDP	4236.28	121.67

5. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed work presents efficient approximate architectures for fundamental arithmetic units, including Full Adders, Compressors, Carry Increment Adders, and Vedic multipliers, which are further applied to the design of an FIR low-pass filter. By strategically introducing controlled approximations, the developed circuits achieve notable reductions in area, power, delay, and Power-Delay Product (PDP) compared to traditional exact designs. Simulation using Cadence tools, functional verification in ModelSim, and FPGA implementation on Xilinx devices collectively validate the practicality and performance benefits of the proposed approach in error-tolerant applications. Overall, the results demonstrate that approximate computing can significantly enhance hardware efficiency while maintaining acceptable computational accuracy.

Looking ahead, the proposed methodology can be extended to larger multiplier architectures, advanced adders, and complete DSP systems such as FFT processors or image-processing pipelines. Future research may explore dynamic or adaptive approximation techniques that adjust accuracy levels based on real-time application requirements. Additionally, integrating machine learning-based error prediction models, investigating low-power approximate architectures for IoT and edge devices, and evaluating performance under different fabrication technologies (e.g., FinFET, sub-7nm nodes) can further broaden the applicability of this work. Such advancements would help establish even more robust and energy-efficient VLSI systems for next-generation computational platforms.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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